

Assessment of Pharmacotherapy for Treatment and Management of Diabetes Mellitus

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Abstract

I gathered and examined the medication histories of 20 patients with diabetes mellitus while doing my clinical pharmacy clerkship rotations in the medical wards at CMH Abbottabad, DHQ Hospital, Haripur, and Yahya Hospital

Haripur. The title of my project was "Assessment of Pharmacotherapy for treatment and management of Diabetes Mellitus". This initiative aimed to evaluate pharmacotherapy for this prevalent chronic illness in order to ensure that medications are used in the community in a safe, acceptable, and economical manner. Diabetes mellitus is a clinical illness marked by abnormalities in the metabolism of proteins, lipids, and carbohydrates as well as persistent hyperglycemia. Defects in either or both of the actions or secretion of insulin may cause the condition. Diabetes Mellitus that is insulin-dependent and non-insulin-dependent. There are two types of diabetes mellitus: primary and secondary. Primary diabetes mellitus is caused by endocrine disorders, drug induced diabetes, and hereditary abnormalities. Common clinical presentations include polyuria, polydipsia, weight loss, blurred vision, paresthesia, and postural hypotension. Diabetic ketoacidosis

(DKA) is one of the immediate problems; retinopathy, nephropathy, and neuropathy are among the chronic sequelae. Insulin and dietary adjustments are part of the therapy of type 1 diabetes. The treatment of type 2 diabetes involves controlling blood sugar levels through diet and taking oral hypoglycemic medications at prescribed dosages, such as glucosidase inhibitors, biguanides, and sulfonylureas. Patient identification and demographic data, the chief complaint history of the current illness, previous surgical history, family history, social history, personal history, clinical laboratory tests, allergies review of systems, physical examination, medication history, including past medication histories, hospital treatment, and discharge medications were among the information gathered from ward histories sheets. Twenty patient's worth of data were gathered, including the patient's demographics, full medical history, medication history, lab results, hospital treatments, monitoring notes, viii discharge drugs, and treatment results. Significant findings of medication history, justification and results of hospitalized pharmacotherapy, identification and management of drug-related issues, and drug information/therapeutic consultation given during hospital rotations were among the key data parameters that were analyzed. Of the twenty patients included in the patient demographic, sixteen were female and four were male. Of the 20 patients included in the patient demographic, 16 were female and 4 were male. Based on the findings, patients between the ages of 50 and 59 are more likely to have disease. Type 2 diabetes, followed by insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus, affected the majority of the patients. Prior to being admitted to the hospital, the patients often took dapagliflozin and metformin; nevertheless, sitagliptin plus metformin was the most commonly prescribed dual therapy combination. Chronic kidney disease, congestive heart failure, and hypertension were co-morbid conditions. The majority of individuals exhibit appropriate

response, according to noteworthy drug history findings. The patients most frequently experienced body pains, dizziness, polydipsia, polyuria, and polyphagia. Insulin (n = 11), biguanides (n = 9), SGLT-2 inhibitors (n = 2), thiazolidinediones (n = 0), DPP-4 inhibitors (n = 4), and sulfonylureas (n = 0) were the most commonly recommended drugs for hospital treatment. Following the examination of diabetic cases, it was found that the majority of patients had interactions in their prescriptions, and that prescriptions may have pharmacological interactions. Based on data from 20 diabetes patients and references to Medscape and Micromedex, it was found that of the interactions, 39.1% were large, 43.4% were moderate, and 17.39% were mild. Additionally, following the examination of diabetic cases, it was found that the majority of patients do not comply with medication therapy because they do not receive adequate assistance and counseling from physicians who are overworked and may not be able to help them. Most patients have uncontrolled diabetes as a result of poor compliance with dietary planning and medication therapy due to a lack of supervision or counseling. The assessment of therapy outcome was conducted using many parameters, including complete blood count, liver and renal function tests, serum electrolytes, and lab tests such as FBS and RBS. This study makes it abundantly evident that clinical pharmacists can be quite helpful in maximizing therapy. Therefore, in a hospital context, a clinical pharmacist is required to justify the therapy.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Diabetes Mellitus

Diabetes comes from the Greek word "siphon" and implies that a lot of urine is made. The second term "mellitus" comes from the Latin word, "Mel" which means "honey"

Diabetes mellitus is defined as an elevated blood glucose associated with absent or inadequate pancreatic insulin secretion, with or without concurrent impairment of insulin action.

1.2. Classification of Diabetes

The disease states underlying the diagnosis of diabetes mellitus are now classified into Four categories:

- Type 1
- Type 2
- Gestational Diabetes Mellitus

A. Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus:

The hallmark of type 1 diabetes is selective beta cell (B cell) destruction and severe or absolute insulin deficiency. Type 1 diabetes is further subdivided into **immune-mediated (type 1a)** and **idiopathic causes (type 1b)**. The immune form is the most common form of type 1 Diabetes although most patients are younger than 30 years of age at the time of diagnosis, the onset can occur at any age. Susceptibility appears to involve a multifactorial genetic linkage, but only 10–15% of patients have a positive family history. Most patients with type 1 Diabetes have one or more circulating antibodies to glutamic acid decarboxylase 65 (GAD 65), insulin autoantibody, tyrosine phosphatase IA2 (ICA 512), and zinc transporter 8 (ZnT8) at the time of diagnosis. These antibodies facilitate the diagnosis of type 1a diabetes and can also be used to screen family members at risk for developing the disease.

They can be treated at first with P/O hypoglycemic agents but then need insulin as their beta cell function declines.

B. Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus

Type 2 diabetes is characterized by tissue resistance to the action of insulin combined with a relative deficiency in insulin secretion. A given individual may have more resistance or more beta-cell deficiency, and the abnormalities may be mild or severe. Although insulin is produced by the beta cells in these patients, it is inadequate to overcome the resistance, and the blood glucose rises. The impaired insulin action also affects fat metabolism, resulting in increased free fatty acid flux and triglyceride levels and reciprocally low levels of high-Density lipoprotein (HDL). Individuals with type 2 diabetes may not require insulin to survive, but 30% or more will benefit from insulin therapy to control blood glucose. In this condition, the blood glucose may rise to 6–20 times the normal range and an altered mental state develops or the person loses consciousness. Urgent medical care and rehydration are required.

Other Specific Types of Diabetes Mellitus

The “other” designation refers to multiple other specific causes of elevated blood glucose: pancreatectomy, pancreatitis, non-pancreatic diseases, drug therapy, etc. For a detailed list the reader is referred to the reference Expert Committee, 2003.

C. Gestational Diabetes Mellitus:

Gestational diabetes (GDM) is defined as any abnormality in glucose levels noted for the first time during pregnancy. Gestational diabetes is diagnosed in approximately 7% of all pregnancies in the USA. During pregnancy, the placenta and placental hormones create an Insulin resistance that is most pronounced in the last trimester. Risk assessment for diabetes is suggested starting at the first prenatal Visit. High-risk women should be screened immediately. Screening may be deferred in lower-risk women until the 24th to 28th week of gestation. [1].

1.3. THE ETIOLOGIES OF DIABETES MELLITUS

- Most common causes of type-1 diabetes are Injury of the β -cells of the pancreas that impair insulin production and can lead to type1 diabetes.
- Viral infections
- Autoimmune disorders may be involved in the destruction of β -cells in many patients with type 1 diabetes
- In some instances, there is a hereditary tendency for β -cells degeneration even without viral infections or autoimmune disorders [2, 3].

Some of the causes of insulin resistance are

- Obesity (especially excess visceral adiposity).
- Excess glucocorticoids (Cushing syndrome or steroid therapy).
- Excess growth hormone (Acromegaly).
- Pregnancy, Gestational diabetes, polycystic ovary disease.
- Lipodystrophy (acquired or genetic lipid accumulation in liver).
- Autoantibodies to the insulin receptor, mutations of insulin receptor.
- Mutations of the peroxisome proliferators activator receptor e.g. PPAR
- Mutations that cause genetic obesity (e.g. Melanocortin receptor mutations) [2,3].

1.4. COMPLICATION OF DIABETES

Figure-1

1.4.1. ACUTE COMPLICATIONS OF DIABETES

Hyperglycemia can cause a variety of signs and symptoms that constitute the acute complications of diabetes. It is important to realize that Type II diabetes and conventionally treated Type I diabetes may be clinically silent, i.e. the affected person has no symptoms of sufficient severity to require seeking medical attention. This is so in at least half of the cases of diabetes in the United States. Persons with clinically silent diabetes are at risk of developing both acute and chronic complications of diabetes.

The classic symptoms of diabetes are polyuria (excessive urine) and polydipsia (excessive thirst). Nocturia (urinating more than once or twice during the night) is a particularly useful symptom because it describes a generally abnormal behavior and is

semi-quantitative. Other typical but less common symptoms include weight loss, polyphagia (excessive appetite) and blurred Vision. A very large number of other symptoms may occur as a result of diabetes, but, in general, these are due to the chronic complications of diabetes. The life-threatening acute complications of diabetes include ketoacidosis and hyperosmolar coma [4]. **Diabetic ketoacidosis** is a syndrome of extremely high blood sugar with resulting dehydration. In addition, co-existing abnormalities of fat metabolism lead to accumulation of acids in the blood. If not treated, diabetic ketoacidosis leads to death within days to weeks. **Hyperosmolar coma** is a virtually identical disorder except that the acid condition of the blood is not present. Ketoacidosis is a common complication of Type I diabetes and a rare complication of Type II diabetes.

1.4.1.1. Pathogenesis of Acute Complications

Hyperglycemia, if sufficiently severe, may lead to glycosuria (glucose in the urine). Normally, the urine is free of glucose unless blood glucose concentrations exceed about 180 mg/dl. Above this threshold, glucose may accumulate in the urine in substantial amounts. If this occurs, urine volume may increase dramatically causing polyuria. Polydipsia occurs as a compensatory mechanism to make up for water lost in the urine. Severe insulin deficiency may lead to breakdown of constituents of body tissue such as fat and muscle which the liver uses to make additional glucose. This condition leads to weight loss and a compensatory polyphagia. Blurred vision occurs in diabetes as a result of marked changes in blood glucose concentration. As the blood glucose rises or falls, the osmotic pressure of blood increases or decreases causing the lens to shrink or swell with resulting changes in the refractive index. In severe diabetes, the loss of water in the urine may exceed the ability of the patient to compensate by drinking more resulting in

extreme dehydration. At the same time body fat is broken down. Certain by-products of fat metabolism are organic acids which cause the blood to become acidic. This combination of circumstances is the cause of diabetic ketoacidosis. Hyperosmolar coma is very similar except that the acid breakdown of body fat with resulting acid production does not occur.

1.4.2. CHRONIC COMPLICATIONS OF DIABETES

Over the course of many years or decades virtually all organs of the body may be damaged as a result of diabetes. The so-called chronic complications of diabetes are usually classified as being due to **microangiopathy** (disease of small blood vessels), **macroangiopathy** (disease of large blood vessels), or neuropathy (damaged nerves). **Microangiopathy** occurs in all tissues but is clinically significant mainly in the back of the eye (retina) and the kidneys. **Diabetic retinopathy** is primarily a sign that can be detected by physical examination and represents the visible changes in the retina which occur as a result of damage to the small blood vessels supplying the eye. If sufficiently severe, diabetic retinopathy can cause impairment of vision and/or blindness. **Diabetic nephropathy** (kidney disease) represents a slow but relentless destruction of the kidneys, leading to kidney failure and the necessity for dialysis or kidney transplant. The **macroangiopathy** of diabetes simply means that persons with high blood sugar, over a long period of time, have a substantially increased risk of developing such conditions as heart attacks, stroke, and gangrene of the feet, which also occur frequently in non-diabetic individuals. **Diabetic neuropathy** is of two types, peripheral and autonomic. **Peripheral neuropathy** typically causes pain and other abnormal sensations in the feet and progressively leads to loss of sensation in affected areas. **Autonomic neuropathy** occurs throughout the body and presents as dysfunction of organ systems regulated by

the autonomic nervous system. Typical symptoms of autonomic neuropathy include dizziness upon standing up, diarrhea, nausea, urinary incontinence, sexual impotence in males, and abnormal sweating.[4]

1.4.2.1. Pathophysiology of Chronic Complications

Currently scientific evidence and opinion strongly support the idea that chronic complications in diabetes stem from prolonged hyperglycemia.

The implication of this latter theory is that treatments directed primarily at long term reduction of blood glucose level would have no impact on the development of the chronic complications.

Hyperglycemia may damage cells and tissues in at least two ways [4]. One theory holds that in tissues such as the eye, the small blood vessels, and the nerves, metabolic breakdown of glucose leads to accumulation of by-products, e.g. sorbitol, which damage these cells. The second theory holds that in hyperglycemia glucose becomes tightly (covalently) bound to structural and functional proteins throughout the body. This attachment of glucose to proteins leads to damage and dysfunction over a long period of time.

1.5. Epidemiology

Diabetes is on the rise worldwide, with a global prevalence in adults in 2017 being 8.8% of world population, with the anticipation of future increase to 9.0% by 2045. In total numbers, this reflects a population of 424.9 million people with diabetes worldwide in 2017. [5]

By 2045, IDF projects that 1 in 8 adults, approximately 783 million will be living in diabetes an increase. of 46%.Out of which over 90% of people with diabetes have type 2 diabetes which is driven by socio economic, demographic, environmental and genetic

factors.[6]

Diabetes around the world in 2021

Approximately 537 million adults (20_79 years) are living with diabetes. The National Diabetes Statistics Report provides upto information on prevalence and incidence of diabetes.38.4 million people have diabetes (11.6% of US population) [7]

Pakistan as world's fifth most populous country, faces numerous health challenges. Among these Diabetes Mellitus stands out as significant health concern due to increasing prevalence and associated health and economic burdens. According to an estimate Pakistan had approximately 5.2 million adults living with diabetes in 2000 and this number amplified to approximately 33million in 2021. [8]. The WHO estimated that in 2016, 58% of all death in Pakistan is due to Diabetes Mellitus.

1.6. Diagnosis of Diabetes

The fasting blood glucose test is the preferred way to diagnose diabetes. It is easy to perform and convenient. After the person has fasted overnight (at least 8 hours), a single sample of blood is drawn and sent to laboratory for analysis.

1) HbA1C

The HbA1C test measures your average blood glucose for past two to three months.

Diabetes is diagnosed at an A1C of greater than or equal to 6.5%

Table -1

2) Fasting Plasma Glucose (FPG)

This test checks your fasting blood glucose levels. Fasting means after not having anything to eat or drink except water for at least 8 hours before test. This test is usually done first thing in morning.

Diabetes is diagnosed at fasting blood glucose of greater than or equal to 126 mg/dl.

Result	Fasting Plasma Glucose
Normal	less than 100mg/dl
Prediabetes	100mg/dl to 125 mg/dl
Diabetes	126 mg/dl

Table-2

3) P/O Glucose Tolerance Test (OGTT)

The OGTT is a two hour test that checks your blood glucose before and two hours after you drink a special sweet drink. It diagnose that how body process sugar. Diabetes is diagnosed at two hour blood glucose or greater than or equal to 200mg/dl.

Result	OGTT
Normal	less than 140mg/dl
Prediabetes	140 to 199 mg /dl
Diabetes	200 mg/dl to higher

Table-3

4) Random / Casual Plasma Glucose Test

This test is blood check at any time of day when you have severe diabetes.

Diabetes is diagnosed at blood glucose of greater than or equal to 200mg/dl.

1.7. Management of Diabetes Mellitus

The management of Diabetes Mellitus involves lifestyle and Pharmacological therapy.

Pharmacological therapy includes insulin and P/O hypoglycemic. Adjustments to diet and increasing exercise may remain the cornerstones for treatment of diabetes. [9]

Goals of Therapy

- Attaining normal blood glucose level

- Reduce Complications
- Increase Quality of life of Patient

1.8. Treatment of Diabetes Mellitus

General Approach

Near normal glycaemia reduces the risk of micro vascular disease complications but aggressive management of traditional cardiovascular risk factors is needed to reduce macro vascular disease risk. Appropriate care requires goal setting for glycaemia, blood pressure, and lipid levels regular monitoring for complications dietary and exercise modifications appropriate self-monitoring of blood glucose (SMBG) and appropriate assessment of laboratory parameters should be maintained.

1.8.1. Non pharmacological Treatment

Medical nutrition therapy is recommended for all patients. For individuals with type 1 DM, the focus is on regulating insulin administration with a balanced diet to achieve and maintain a healthy body weight. A meal plan that is moderate in carbohydrates and low in saturated fat, with a focus on balanced meals is recommended. In addition, patient with type 2 DM often require caloric restrictions to promote weight loss. Bedtime and between meal snacks are not usually if pharmacologic management is appropriate.

Aerobic exercise can improve insulin resistance and glycemic control in most patients and may reduce cardiovascular risk factors, contribute to weight loss or maintenance and improve well-being. Exercise should be started slowly in previously sedentary patients. Older patients and those with atherosclerosis disease should have a cardiovascular evaluation prior to beginning a substantial exercise program.[10] The blood glucose level is closely affected by carbohydrate intake. Daily intake should be kept fairly constant, and the amount given should be appropriate to the level of physical

activity. Most active young people will require 180g of carbohydrate per day, while 100 may be sufficient for an elderly person.

Major reason for increasing the proportion of calories as carbohydrates is to reduce fat intake. Since there is an increased risk of death from coronary artery disease in diabetes, it is wise to restrict saturated fats and to substitute unsaturated fats. Most patients benefit from increased physical activity. Aerobic exercise can improve insulin resistance and glycemic control and may reduce cardiovascular risk factors, contribute to weight loss or maintenance, and improve well-being. Exercise should be started slowly in previously sedentary patients. Older patients and those with atherosclerotic disease should have a cardiovascular evaluation prior to beginning a substantial exercise program. [9,10,12].

Figure-2 (Non pharmacological treatment)

1.8.2. Pharmacological Treatment

Figure-3 (Pharmacological treatment)

1.8.2.1. INSULIN

CLASS	TYPE		ONSET (minutes)	PEAK (hours)	DURATION (hours)
Rapid acting insulin	Lispro		15-30	0.5-2.5	3-4
	Aspart			1-3	3-5
	Gulisine			1-2	3-4
	Recombinant human insulin regular		12-15	1	2.5-3
Short acting insulin	Soluble insulin	regular (only type that can be given intravenously)	30-60	2-3	3-6
Intermediate acting insulin	Neutral		2-4hours	4-6	8-12
	Protamine Hagedorn(NPH)				
Long acting insulin	Glargin Detemir		4-5hours	flat	22-24

Table-4

Insulin is necessary for type 1 diabetes and for type 2 diabetes who are inadequately controlled or during periods of stress. Insulin is also used in gestational diabetics inadequately controlled by diet and exercise. There are various types of insulin based on onset and duration of action, as well as premixed products. Generally, mixing of insulin

should be discouraged.

Insulin, glargine and detemir may not be mixed with any other insulin. Insulin is **stable** for 28 days once opened, (with the exception of detemir, which is stable for 42 days) and can be stored in or out of the refrigerator. Although, generally, pens in use are not stored in the refrigerator, the goal of any insulin regimen or combination is to target control, avoid hypoglycemia, and be acceptable to the patient. Consider insulin therapy, when HbA1c >8% and the patient is already on combination or triple therapy and exhibits hyperglycemia. P/O agents are often continued if a once or twice daily insulin regimen is chosen.

Although premixed insulin offers the advantage of decreased injection that is difficult to adjust either insulin component successfully. **Insulin dosage:** can be adjusted every 3-7 days on the basis of patient self-monitoring of blood glucose. However, the patient who has developed an understanding of the process will adjust more frequently to manage changes in lifestyle, such as intensive exercise or larger

Insulin regimens are often tailored to fit preferences and lifestyle. Initiation of insulin therapy can be a challenging concept and patients need to adjust. There may be benefits in starting on a once or twice daily regime and moving on 4 times a day if control is difficult.

Insulin Pens: Insulin pens offer flexibility in patient schedule as they are more discreet and may offer an alternative to those who peer injections or have dexterity or visual impairments. Pens are either disposable or have replaceable cartridges. . Pen holds 300 units (3 ml) of insulin, and common boxes of **Stability** of insulin pen contents in use is usually 28 days, but this should be checked with the SPC as there are variations.

1.8.2.2. NON INSULIN ANTIDAIBETIC AGENT

(1). BIGUANIDES

GENERIC NAME	MECHANISM OF ACTION	TARGET AREA	DOSING STRATEGY	ADVERSE DRUG REACTIONS
Metformin	Decreases hepatic glucose production, Decreases GI glucose absorption, Increases Target cell insulin sensitivity.	Liver	500mg/day to twice daily with meals Advance weekly to a maximum of 2000-2550mg/day	Gastrointestinal: Diarrhea, Abdominal Pain, Flatulence, Indigestion Lactic Acidosis Low serum vitamin B-12
Metformin ER	500-1000 mg/ day; dose may be increased by 500 mg weekly to a maximum of 2000 mg/day			

(2). SULPHONYLUREAS

GENERIC NAME	MECHANISM OF ACTION	TARGET AREA	DOSING STRATEGY	ADVERSE DRUG REACTIONS
1st Generation	Initial effect to increase insulin secretion from beta cells	Pancreas	1) 100—500mg once daily Max.750mg/day	Hypoglycemia Weight gain
1.Chlorpropamide				
2.Tolbutamide		May	2) 1000—2000mg once daily	

	also decrease rate	Max.3000mg/day	
3.Tolazamide	of hepatic glucose production and increase insulin receptor sensitivity	250-500mgonce daily Max.1000mg/day	
2nd Generation:			Hypoglycemia
1.Glimepride		1. 1—2mg with Breakfast increase by 2 mg every 1—2 weeks to a max of 8 mg/day	
2.Glyburide (Or <i>Glibenclamide</i>) micronase		2. 1.5-3mg/day with breakfast increase by 1.5 mg weekly to a maximum of 12 mg/day	
3.Gluburide		3.2.5-5mg/day with breakfast Increase by 2.5 mg weekly to a maximum of 20 mg/day	
4.Glipizide	4. 5mg/day 30 minutes before a meal	Increase by 5 mg weekly to a maximum of 40 mg/day;	Weight gain

(3). MEGLITINIDES

GENERIC NAME	MECHANISM OF ACTION	TARGET AREA	DOSING STRATEGY	ADVERSE DRUG REACTIONS
Repaglinide	Increases insulin secretion via binding K ⁺ channels on β islet cells. Reduces postprandial hyperglycemia. Amount of insulin released is dependent upon existing glucose levels.	Pancreas	0.5mg 15-30 minutes before each meal Double pre-prandial dose every 7 days to 4mg/dose or 16mg/day (To be taken only if eating)	Diarrhea. Weight gain. Edema, particularly in Patients with HTN & congestive cardiac failure. Arthropathy Hypoglycemia
Nateglinide			120mg three Times daily before meals (To be taken only if eating)	

(4). THIAZOLIDINEDIONES

GENERIC NAME	MECHANISM OF ACTION	TARGET AREA	DOSING STRATEGY	ADVERSE DRUG REACTIONS
Rosiglitazone	Insulin sensitizing agent that primarily activates the peroxisome proliferator-activated gamma [PPAR (gamma)] nuclear receptors, thereby enhancing peripheral glucose utilization and improving glycemic control. It is also involved in the regulation of fatty acid metabolism.	Peripheral Tissue	4mg twice daily or in two divided doses	Upper Respiratory Tract Infections Weight Gain
Pioglitazone			15-30mg; day Increase after 12weeks to a Max. 45mg/day	

(5). α -GLUCOSIDASE INHIBITORS

GENERIC NAME	MECHANISM OF ACTION	TARGET AREA	DOSING STRATEGY	ADVERSE DRUG REACTIONS
Acarbose	P/O pancreatic alpha-amylase and intestinal brush border alpha-glycosidase. This results in delayed hydrolysis of ingested complex carbohydrates and disaccharides and absorption of glucose. Inhibits metabolism of sucrose to glucose and fructose.	Brush Border of Small Intestine	25 mg three times daily with first bite of each main meal Advance at 4-8 week intervals to a maximum of 100 mg three times daily 25 mg three times daily	Abdominal Pain Diarrhea, Flatulence Elevated serum Transaminases Hematologic: Serum Iron Low Abdominal Pain Diarrhea Flatulence
Miglitol				

(6). SODIUM-GLUCOSE TRANSPORTER (SGLT)-2 INHIBITOR

GENERIC NAME	MECHANISM OF ACTION	TARGET AREA	DOSING STRATEGY	ADVERSE REACTIONS	DRUG
Canagliflozin	Selective sodium-glucose transporter-2 (SGLT2) inhibitor expressed in the proximal renal tubules, is responsible for the majority of the reabsorption of filtered glucose from the tubular lumen; SGLT2 inhibitors will reduce glucose reabsorption and lower the renal threshold for glucose, thereby increasing	Kidney	100 mg/day in the morning; may increase to 300 mg/day	Hyperkalemia, genitourinary infection, hypervolemia, renal insufficiency, hypotension	
Dapagliflozin	reabsorption of filtered glucose from the tubular lumen; SGLT2 inhibitors will reduce glucose reabsorption and lower the renal threshold for glucose, thereby increasing		5mg/day in the morning; may increase to 10mg/day	Genitourinary infection, hypervolemia/ hypotension, dysuria, polyuria, dyslipidemia, mild hypoglycemia, nasopharyngitis	

<p>Empagliflozin urinary glucose excretion</p> <p>Also reduces sodium reabsorption and increases the delivery of sodium to the distal tubule; this may influence several physiological functions, such as lowering both pre- and afterload of the heart and down regulating sympathetic activity</p>	<p>10 mg/day</p> <p>in the morning may increase to 25 mg/day</p>	<p>Genitourinary infection, hypervolemia/hypotension, dysuria polyuria, mild hypoglycemia,</p>
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(6). DIPEPTIDYL PEPTIDASE (DDP)-4 INHIBITORS

GENERIC NAME	MECHANISM OF ACTION	TARGET AREA	DOSING STRATEGY	ADVERSE DRUG REACTIONS
Sitagliptin	Dipeptidyl peptidase-4 (DPP-4) enzyme inhibitor, protects glucose-dependent insulintropic polypeptide (GIP) and	Brush Border of Small Intestine	100mg/day	Upper respiratory tract Infection, Diarrhea UTI, headache arthralgia,

Saxagliptin	glucagon-like peptide (GLP-1) from inactivation, thereby enhancing their actions; this increases insulin release and	2.5-5mg/day	nasopharyngitis Headache, increased ALT greater than three times ULN (upper limit normal),
Linagliptin	decreases glucagon levels in the circulation	5mg/day	nasopharyngitis, upper respiratory
Alogliptin	in a glucose-dependent manner	25mg/day	Upper Respiratory Tract Infection

Oral Agents

Second Generation Sulfonylureas

Mechanism: Stimulate the Insulin release from binding to suddenly urea B cells

Target post prandial glucose

Place in therapy, monotherapy, combination therapy can be first line

Reduction in HbA1c =0.9 _ 2.5%

Examples Gliclazide, Glibenclamide

Risks: hypoglycemia, weight gain

No additional benefits at doses>50% of maximum dose.

Figure-4(Sulphonylurea)

Biguanides

Mechanism: decrease gluconeogenesis and increase peripheral utilisation of glucose

Target fasting blood glucose

Place in therapy: considered first line, monotherapy, combination therapy.

Reduction in HbA1c =1_1.3%

Available as metformin immediate release and extended release (MR); no real advantage over standard formulation.

Increase dose by 500mg/ day weekly

Maximum effective dose is 2000mg/day

Does not cause hypoglycemia

Decrease macro vascular events

Diabetes Medication Biguanide
Biguanide diabetes medication lowers the amount of glucose made by the liver; thus lower blood-glucose levels.

Figure-5(Biguanides)

Meglitinides

Mechanism: Stimulate insulin release from binding to sulfonylurea beta-cell site.

Target post prandial glucose; short-acting. Place in therapy, monotherapy, or combination therapy.

Reduction in HbA1c = 0.6 to 0.8 % Example, repaglinide, nateglinide

Risks : hypoglycemia and weight gain.

The need for frequent dosing may adversely affect compliance.

Figure-6 (Maglitinide)

Thiazolidinedione

Mechanism :Activate PPAR-G, (Peroxisome Proliferator Activated Receptor Gamma), increasing peripheral insulin sensitivity in skeletal muscle cells

Target fasting blood glucose

Place in therapy considered second line but could be monotherapy in patients with lower HbA1c range,(6.5 to 8%)h combination therapy,

Reduction in HbA1c is equal to 1.5 to 1.6%.

Example is Pioglitazone

Edema and weight gain occur more in combination with insulin.

Figure-7(Thiazolidinediaones)

Alpha Glycosidase Inhibitors

Mechanism: Slow carbohydrate absorption in gut • Target postprandial glucose •

Place in therapy, monotherapy, or combination therapy •

Reduction in HbA1c, 0.6-1.3% •

Example: Acarbose

Must take with carbohydrate containing meal •

Decrease postprandial glucose must be taken with first bite of food •

Start low and go slow to avoid GI intolerance

If Hypoglycemia occurs (Risk if on insulin and sulphonylurea), Must treat with glucose, not sucrose, or acarbose interferes with sucrose absorption.

Figure-8(Alpha glucosidase inhibitor)

Dipeptidyl Peptidase Inhibitors (DPP IV)

Mechanism : Slows inactivation of incretin hormone GLP-4 suppressing glucagon secretion and increasing glucose-dependent insulin release,

Target postprandial blood glucose,

Place in therapy; monotherapy or combination therapy,

Reduction in HbA1c 0.8%,

Example : Sitagliptin and Vildagliptin. Dosage adjustment necessary in renal dysfunction, increase satiety, delay gastric emptying, weight neutral.

Newer Antidiabetic Treatments**Exenatide**

Glucagon-like peptide 1, GLP-1, incretin mimetic; incretin hormone given by injection

Mechanism.

Stimulate insulin secretion in response to glucose load.

Inhibit release of glucagon following a meal.

Increases satiety.

Slows absorption of nutrients through delayed gastric emptying.

Plays in therapy; adjunct therapy for use in combination with sulfonylurea, metformin, or a combination of these.

Reduction in HbA1c; 0.8-0.9%.

Common side effects include nausea and vomiting that are dose-related.

Recent reports of possible exenatoid pancreatitis have arisen. [11,12]

2. AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

i. To assure the rationalization of pharmacotherapy by accessing the prescription from CMH Abbottabad, DHQ Hospital Haripur and Yahya Hospital Haripur.

- ii. Evaluation of diverse drug therapy problems, drug-drug interactions, polypharmacy, untreated conditions, over- or under-use, and adverse drug reactions.
- iii. To ensure safe, appropriate, and cost-effective utilization of medicine.
- iv. to identify problems in prescribing practices that may necessitate intervention and to analyse them for any potential drug interactions.
- v. To ensure the provision of medication according to standard treatment guidelines.
- vi. To appraise the safety measures for further prevention of diabetes mellitus.
- vii. To determine the desired clinical outcomes of drug therapy.
- viii. To monitor the accurate drug utilization review in order to enhance patient compliance.
- ix. To be aware about the most prescribed drug and to consult the patient.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. STUDY DESIGN

Sample Taken

The study was conducted at multicenter healthcare setting including:

1. DHQ Hospital Haripur
2. CMH Abbottabad
3. Yahya Hospital Haripur

Random prescriptions were collected from these hospitals.

- **Sample Size**

Sample of 21 prescriptions was collected.

- **Method**

The methodology adopted to collect data was same from the three places:

➤ Data Collection

Patients admitted to hospital during the said period were included in this work.

Following data were collected:

- Patient's Demographics Information
- Chief Complaints
- History Of Present Illness
- Past Medical History
- Past Surgical History
- Family History
- Personal History
- Allergies
- Medication History
- Laboratory Data
- Diagnosis
- Drug-Therapy Provided In the Hospital
- Monitoring Notes
- Discharge Medications
- Treatment Outcomes
- Other Patient Information

3.2. CASE HISTORIES

Total 20 Case Histories of patients suffering from Diabetes Mellitus were recorded in this hospital based study.

Inclusion Criteria: 20 Case histories of patients diagnosed with Diabetes Mellitus who were admitted in the Medical ward of the CMH Abbottabd, DHQ Hospital

Haripur, and Yahya Hospital Haripur, were recorded for this study. There were no gender restrictions however children below 10 years of age were not included.

Exclusion Criteria: lincomplete case histories were excluded from the study and also the patient with age less than 10 years were also excluded from the study.

3.3. DATA COLLECTION AND CASE EVALUATION

Medication history of each patient was analyzed for drug allergies, response, undesirable effects, compliance and its application in the assessment & management of patient's current medical problems.

Current therapy provided in the hospital was analyzed for its indications and clinical outcomes. The whole medication therapy provided in the hospital was analyzed for the drug related problems and their management. **Micromedex & Medscape** is used to analyze drug-drug interactions in prescription of diabetes patients. Any drug information/therapeutic-consultation or patient education and counseling that were provided during rotations were also reported.

3.4. Result Interpretation

Microsoft Excel was used to graphically present the data and perform various statistical calculations.

The following calculations were performed:

- Gender distribution of the disease in the recorded cases.
- Age distribution.
- Number of interactions per prescription.
- Types of interaction on the basis of severity.
- Drug related problems in medication histories.
- Co-Morbid conditions in patients suffering from diabetes.

- Frequency of Medication in prescription of diabetes patient etc.

4. CASE-WISE ANALYSIS

Case # 1

1. PATIENT DEMOGRAPHIC DATA:

PATIENT NAME: Najar AGE: 65 -year GENDER: Female

2. DISEASE PROFILE:

CHIEF COMPLAINTS	PAST MEDICAL HISTORY	CLINICAL VITAL SIGNS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diabetic Foot • Fever (For 5 days) • Headache • Leg pain 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diabetes (Past 10 years) • Hypertension 	BP:130/90mmHg PULSE:78/min TEMP:98F

PAST SURGICAL HISTORY: No Surgical History

FAMILY HISTORY: Family History of DM Type II, Hypertension

SOCIO-ECONOMIC HISTORY: Satisfactory

ALLERGIES: No known drug allergies

MEDICATION HISTORY:

On Oral Hypoglycemic agents for years. Insulin was added recently.

3. LAB TEST:

TESTS	NORMAL VALUES	MEASURED VALUES
Glucose (Random)	75-140mg/dl	375mg/dl
HbA1C	4-6.6%	14%
Blood urea	18-45mg/dl	14mg/dl
ALT	10-50U/L	19U/L

Alkaline phosphates	30-120U/L	106U/L
Creatinine	0.7-1.4mg/dl	0.9mg/dl

4. FINAL DIAGNOSIS

- Uncontrolled Diabetes Mellitus Type II leading to Diabetic foot.

Fig 1

5. MEDICATION CHART:

DURING HOSPITALIZATION:

Medications	Dose	Frequency	Route	Remarks
Inj.Vancomycin	1G	OD	IV	<p>Indications: Bacterial Infection (skin and skin structure infection)</p> <p>RD: 2g divided either as 500mgQ6H or 1g Q12H</p> <p>MOU: Dilute 500mg with ≥ 100ml of diluent and 1g ≥ 200ml of diluent</p>
Inj.Humulin R	10 Units	TDS	S/C	<p>Indications: Treatment of diabetes mellitus Type 2</p> <p>RD: 0.7-2.5 unit/kg/day</p> <p>MOU: Should be given subcutaneously</p>
Inf.Ringer lactate	500ml	OD	IV	Indications:
Inf.Pladex (Paracetamol)	100ml (1gram)	STAT	IV	<p>Indications: pyrexia</p> <p>RD: 650mgQ4H or 1000mgQ6H Max</p>

				Single dose: 1000mg/dose
				Max Dose: dose/day=4g
				MOU: Administered by IV infusion over 15 minutes
Tab.tervimate(XR) (Metformin+sitagliptin)	50/500mg	OD (at dinner)	P/O	Indications: Hypoglycemic agent for type II DM
				Drug Class: Metformin: Biguanides Sitagliptin: dipeptidyl peptidase-IV inhibitor
				RD: sitagliptin 100mg metformin 2000mg per day
				Limitation of use: Not recommended in patients with type I DM.

UPON DISCHARGE:

Medications	Dose	Frequency	Route
Inj. Humulin R (Insulin regular human)	10 Unit (Pre breakfast, pre-lunch, pre- dinner)	TDS	S/C
Tab. Terviamet (XR) (Metformin=sitagliptin)	50/500mg	OD(After dinner)	P/O

SELECTION OF THERAPY:

- **Human Regular Insulin:** To control postprandial blood glucose level.
- **Inj. Vancomycin:** To reduce bacterial infection.
- **Metformin+Sitagliptin:** To control high blood glucose.

6. CASE ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION:

- **COMPLIANCE:** Poor
- **RESPONSE:** Condition improved slowly
- **ADRs:** No ADRs reported
- **FOOD PLAN:** No written food plan was given to the patient
- **PATIENT EDUCATION AND COUNSELING:** No Written Information was given.

DRUG RELATED PROBLEMS:**(a) DRUG INTERACTIONS:**

No significant drug interaction is observed.

(b) DOSE:

The dose of insulin was calculated on experience and not considering the body weight

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

The patient presented with symptoms of fever, headache, leg pain and diabetic foot. She has a medical history of hypertension and Diabetes. She was diagnosed as a condition of uncontrolled Diabetes Mellitus type II. She got treatment. Drug interaction was not found.

CASE#2

1. PATIENT DEMOGRAPHIC DETAIL:

Patient name	Dildar khan
Age	50 years
Address	Mansehra

2. HISTORY OF PRESENT ILLNESS:

Chief complaints	PAST MEDICAL HISTORY (PMH)	CLINICAL INVESTIGATIONS
Uncontrolled sugar BP, Weight loss, Asthenia	Diabetes from past 7 year, Hypertension	BP: 200/100 mm of Hg Weight: 63kg Chest, CNS, CVS, Abdomen; clear

Past Surgical History: (PSH): Nill

Family History : Diabetes mellitus and Hypertension

Socio-economic History : Satisfactory

Allergies : Nill

3. LAB. TESTS

Tests	Normal values	Observed values
Glucose (Random)	70-140 mg/dl	273mg/dl
Creatinine	Male 0.7-1.1 mg/dl	1.25mg/dl
Cholesterol	<200mg/dl	188mg/dl
Triglyceride	<150mg/dl	397.8mg/dl
Uric acid	Male 3.5-7.0mg/dl	4.7mg/dl
CBC (RBC)	4.00-5.50/ul	6.10/ul
MCHC	31.6-35.4pg	3708pg
HCT	12-18g/dl	19.8g/dl
URINE R/E		
SUGAR	NILL	++
ALBUMIN	NILL	TRACE
RBC	NILL	1-2
PUS CELL	NILL	2-3
EPITHELIAL CELL	NILL	1-2

4. FINAL DIAGNOSIS:

According to lab test and physical examination patient have Uncontrolled Diabetes Mellitus Type-2 Hypertension, UTI infection, hypertriglyceridemia.

5. MEDICATION CHART:

MEDICATIONS	DOSAGE			ROUTE	REMARKS
	DOSE	FREQUENCY			
Inj insuget 70/30 (NPH 70% &30% regular insulin)	20 unit in morning and 10 unit in night	BD	S/C	Indication: Insulin dependent Diabetes or NIDDM RD: According to the severity Of DM MOU: inject through SC route	
Tab viptin met (vidagliptin and metformin)	50 mg/500mg	BD	P/O	Indications: Hypoglycemic agent for Type 2 Diabetes RD: vidagliptin 50mg & metformin 2000mg Per day	
Tab sofvasc-v (amlodipine and valartan)	10mg/160mg	OD	P/O	Indications: HTN RD: Max 10/160 mg OD MOU: Administer without regard to meal	
Tab morcet (escitalopram)	5mg	OD	P/O	Indication: relieve pain RD:5mg OD	
Tab loprin (Aspirin)	75mg	OD	P/O	Indication: Ischemic Event(unstable angina, MI) RD: 75-325mg daily MOU: Take this	

Cap roteric (pregabalin)	75mg	OD	P/O	medication after food Indication: Neuropathic pain, epilepsy and generalized anxiety disorder RD: 50mg,75mg,100mg,150 mg once daily MOU: administer orally with or without food
Tab AND6 (mecobalamin Vit B12)	500mcg	BD	P/O	Indication: for vit B12 deficiency
Capcidol F lotion (capsicum extract)	60ml	BD		Indication: for muscle and joints pain
Tab Rucal (supplement)	500mg+250IU	OD	P/O	Indication: For vitamin D and calcium deficiency Indication Hyperlipidemia:
Tab Rosera (Resuvastatin)	20mg	OD	P/O	RD: 5-20mg/day MOU: Take with or without food

6. CASE ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

- **COMPLIANCE:** Good
- **RESPONSE:** Improving condition
- **ADRS:** hypoglycemia
- **FOOD PLAN:** No food plan was given to the patient
- **PATIENT EDUCATION AND COUNSELING:** No written information was provided

7. DRUG RELATED PROBLEMS

a). DRUG INTERACTIONS:

The combination of insulin, oral anti diabetic agent and Aspirin may increase (major) the risk of hypoglycemia and concurrent use of metformin and amlodipine may result in increased (moderate) risk of hyperglycemia and potential loss of glycemic control.

b). DOSE:

All doses of drugs are correct

8. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The patient presented with symptoms of uncontrolled sugar, weight loss, asthenia and BP. He was diagnosed as a condition of uncontrolled diabetes Mellitus type-2, Hypertension and UTI infection. The patient response to the therapy was satisfactory after starting it and good compliance was shown by him due to which his condition was improving but there is no medicine for UTI infection. Although there was an interaction between P/O ant diabetic agent, aspirin and Insulin but it didn't cause any significant harm to the patient. Due to his good condition, the patient was discharged from the hospital with medications to take at home.

LIST OF CASES

SERIAL NO.	PATIENT NAME	AGE	GENDER	DIAGNOSIS
1	Najar	65 years	female	DM Type 2 leading to diabetic foot
2	Dildar khan	50 years	male	DM Type 2,HTN,UTI
3	Sameena bibi	59 years	female	DM Type 2,HTN,UTI
4	Naseem Akhtar	60 years	female	DM Type 2 leading to diabetic foot
5	Mumtaz bibi	52 years	female	DM type 2 and diabetic neuropathy
6	Mehraj bibi	37 years	female	DM type 2,HTN
7	Hakeem jan	50 years	female	DM type 2
8	Kanez Akhtar	56 years	female	DM Type 2 leading to diabetic foot, acute gastroenteritis
9	Hassan	28 years	male	DM TYPE 1
10	Asif	26 years	male	DM TYPE 1
11	Firdous	70 years	female	DM Type 2 leading to diabetic foot,
12	Sumaira	37 years	female	Gestational Diabetes Amenorrhea
13	Abdullah	55 years	male	DM Type 2 leading to diabetic foot
14	Sajida rani	55 years	female	DM type 2

15	Parveen bibi	60 years	female	DM Type 2,HTN,IHD
16	Nor un Nisa	70 years	female	DM type 2
17	Shamim Akhtar	65 years	female	DM Type 2 eading to diabetic foot
18	Nighat bibi	56 years	female	DM type 2,AfI
19	Rabia rashid	38 years	female	Gestational Diabetes
20	Farzana bibi	55 years	female	DM type 2,IHD

5. RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

5.1 STATISTICAL INTERPRETATION

The study was conducted from April 2024 to May 2024. Among 20 histories prevalence of disease among male and female and different age groups were determined. With the detailed study of patient condition, therapy related problems, treated and untreated condition of patient were also observed.

5.1.1 Gender Wise Prevalence of Diabetes in DHQ Hospital Haripur

Case histories of the selected patient having diabetes admitted in hospital were divided into two groups on the basis of gender, such as Group A (Male), Group B (Female). The study showed that 13 patients were male while 15 patients of diabetes were female. Frequency and percentage of diabetes in gender distribution among case histories is given in table

GENDER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
MALE PATIENTS	4	20%
FEMALE PATIENTS	16	80%
TOTAL	20	100 %

GENDER WISE DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS

5.1.2 Frequency Distribution Of Diabetes According to Gender:

Discussion: As seen by the data female patients are more in numbers who have been affected by diabetes as compared to male patients. Male patients were in number 4 and female patients were 16 in number who suffered from diabetes.

FREQUENCY OF GENDER WISE DISTRIBUTION

5.1.3. Age Wise Prevalence Of Diabetes In District Head Quarter (DHQ) Hospital Haripur, CMH Abbottabad, Life care Hospital & Yahya Hospital Haripur:

Case histories of selected patients having diabetes admitted in District Head Quarter (DHQ) Hospital Haripur, CMH Abbottabad, life care hospital & Yahya Hospital Haripur were divided into six groups on the basis of age, such as Group A (20-29 years), Group B (30-39 years) Group C (40-49 years) and Group D (50-59 years) Group E (60-69 years)

Group F (70-79 years).Frequency and percentage of diabetes patients in these age groups were given in the following table.

Table 5.1.3. Percentage and Frequency distribution of Diabetes according to age

AGE IN YEARS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
20-29 years	2	10%
30-39 years	3	15%
40-49 years	0	0%
50-59 years	9	45%
60-69 years	4	20%
70-79 years	2	10%

Table 5.1.4 Frequency and Percentage Wise Distribution of DRPS In Medication Histories:

S. NO	DRUG RELATED PROBLEM	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1	DRUG INTERACTION	23	51%
2	ADVERSE DRUG REACTION	4	8.8%
3	NON COMPLIANCE	2	4.4%
4	THERAPEUTIC DUPLICATION	0	0%
5	CONDITION UNTREATED	2	4.4%

6	DRUG WITHOUT INDICATION	4	8.8%
7	POLYPHARMACY	2	4.4%
8	WRONG DOSAGE REGIEME	8	17.7%
	TOTAL	45	

5.1.5. TYPES OF INTERACTION ON THE BASIS OF SEVERITY:

Total number of interactions in all patients' prescription were 23 among these 9 were major interactions while 10 interactions were moderate. There were 4 minor interactions.

Table Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Types of Interaction Based On Severity:

TYPES OF INTERACTION	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
MAJOR	9	39.1%
MODERATE	10	43.4%
MINOR	4	17.39%
TOTAL	23	100%

TABLE 5.1.6. Co-Morbid Conditions in Patients Suffering from Diabetes:

Co-Morbid Conditions	No of Cases
Nil	8
AFI	1
Hypertension	4

Ischemic Heart Disease	2
Chronic Hepatitis	1
UTI	2
Acute gastroenteritis	1
Anemia	1

Discussion: After the analysis of diabetes cases, it was observed that prescriptions have higher frequency of hypertension as co-morbid condition in patients suffering from diabetes.

Table 5.1.7. FREQUENCY OF DIFFERENT DRUGS PRESCRIBED FOR DIABETIC PATIENTS

ANTIDIABETIC DRUGS:

(MONO AND DUAL THERAPY)

Dapagliflozin	1
Metformin	5
Sitagliptin	1
linagliptin	1
Sitagliptin+Metformin	2
Empagliflozin+Metformin	1
vidagliptin and metformin	1

Table 5.1.8. Frequency of Prescribing Of Different Classes of OHG

CLASS NAME	FREQUENCY
Biguanides	9
SGLT-2 inhibitors	2
Thiazolidinediones	0
DPP-4 inhibitors	4
Sulfonylureas	0

Table 5.1.9 Prescribing of Different Types of Insulin

Prescribing of Insulin	Frequency	Percentage
Regular Insulin	11	68%
Insulin Isophane + Insulin Regular 70/30	3	19%
Insulin Glargine	2	12%

TABLE 5.1.11. FREQUENCY OF PATIENT HAVE DAIBETIC COMPLICATION:

COMPLICTION IN PATIENT	FREQUENCY
Diabetic foot	6
Diabetic neuropathy	1
Nephropathy	0
Retinopathy	0
Diabetic ketoacidosis	1
HTN	4
Coronary artery disease	2

CONCLUSION

In the course of my extensive research on diabetes mellitus, it was reported that there are a variety of drug-related problems. The frequency and percentage of cases of DRPs were then computed in a tabular format after patient medication history data was gathered and analyzed by comparing prescribed medications with recommended guidelines. Three main categories of DRPs were identified in diabetes mellitus histories: untreated conditions, polypharmacy, and drug interactions. The most crucial finding was that drug interactions were the most common DRPs, despite the fact that drug prescriptions are the primary cause of morbidity and death.

It can be concluded that mutual interaction between physicians, surgeons, other health care professionals, and clinical pharmacists is time-sensitive and necessary to ensure rational medication therapy and the desired outcomes, i.e., positive response to therapy of every patient, in order to provide safe, effective, appropriate, and cost-effective therapy to individual patients and the entire community. Patient education and counseling is crucial to patient compliance, and pharmacists have a responsibility to inform and counsel patients regarding the dosage, frequency, and duration of their medications. the patient to contact their doctor in the event of any adverse effects, as well as information about the dosage form, administration method, and possible side effects.

Following the examination of diabetes cases, it was found that the majority of patients do not comply with medication therapy because they do not receive adequate guidance and counseling from physicians who are overworked and may not be able to help them. Most patients experience poor compliance and uncontrolled diabetes as a

result of inadequate guidance or counseling regarding diet plans and medication therapy.

When prescribing medication, it is important to consider drug interactions and to note the significance of such interactions if the drugs are necessary for a specific condition. It should be encouraged to prescribe antibiotics following the completion of the culture sensitivity test. When a patient has liver or renal impairment, their medication dosage needs to be adjusted to reduce side effects and, consequently, morbidity and mortality. Finally, proper management and supervision of narrow therapeutic drugs by pharmacists should be implemented.

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